

Good practice of community media and media participation in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia

in line with the findings of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy

Credit: Petra Moser/FRO

Community media supporting citizens **participation in the media** are fundamental to a pro-democratic media policy. This is evident from the resolutions adopted by the four Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, held in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia between March and May 2025.

Citizens' parliaments on Media and Democracy were organised as part of the project **Mapping Media for Future Democracies** (MeDeMAP), involving partners from academia and civil society in ten EU countries. All teams examined the relationship between media and democracy and citizens' demand for more participation. The research project was coordinated by the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW) and funded by the Horizon Europe programme.

Each of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy comprised 20 citizens. These were organised by COMMIT (Austria), Charles University (Czech Republic), Mary Immaculate College (Ireland) and the Peace Institute (Slovenia). During four sessions dedicated to the topics of media and democracy, systems, representation, and participation, the citizens adopted resolutions in support of media policies that would strengthen democracy in their respective countries. Further details of the sessions can be found on the Citizens' Parliaments' blog <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

Community media originate locally and use horizontal production structures, enabling people to create their own means of cultural expression, news, information and dialogue. They encourage debate within and outside of communities, promote democratic participation and contribute to a diverse media landscape. The Council of Europe recognises the value of community media as a source of local content, cultural and linguistic diversity, media pluralism, social inclusion and intercultural dialogue.

In line with the resolutions adopted by the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, examples of good practice of community media supporting citizen participation in the media are presented from **Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia**.

Austria

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy emphasised the importance of greater diversity within the media landscape. They also highlighted the need for increased public support for community media to encourage civic participation and strengthen democracy.

The **Association of Community Broadcasters in Austria** (Verband Freier Rundfunk Österreich) was founded in 1993 and brings together 14 non-commercial community radio stations and three community TV stations with up to 5000 active citizens involved. It runs an online platform where all involved citizens can upload their radio productions and make them available as podcasts for further distribution and exchange.

The association organises the annual School Radio Day.
<https://www.freier-rundfunk.at/schulradiotage.html>

Thematic focus week with participation of all community broadcasters.
<https://www.freier-rundfunk.at/themenswerpunkte.html>

The "Land of Free Media" initiative: With its five independent, non-commercial radio stations and a community TV station, Upper Austria is the Austrian federal state with the greatest diversity of com-

munity media. DORFTV, Radio FRO, Freies Radio Freistadt, Freies Radio Salzkammergut, Freies Radio B138, and FRI - Freies Radio Innviertel – have joined forces to form the “Land of Free Media” initiative. Together, they create media spaces for debates about politics and society, helping citizens to shape them. <https://landderfreienmedien.at>

The Czech Republic

The Czech Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy recognises the importance of community media and is calling for a media law that would grant official status and funding to media projects created by local or minority groups, including training initiatives. It also calls on the media to enable citizens to participate more in news creation.

Radio R

Radio R is a community radio station based at Masaryk University in Brno. Since its establishment in 2008, it has operated as a non-commercial, alternative and open platform, emphasising community building and creative expression. Radio R enables its members to create programmes covering diverse and minority topics, and offers students and volunteers without professional backgrounds hands-on experience in broadcasting.

Radio R <https://medzur.fss.muni.cz/studentska-media/radio-r>

Romea.cz

Romea.cz is a key community media outlet for the Roma community. Publishing news in both print and online formats, it reports on politics, culture, and human rights and highlights Roma perspectives, which are often absent from Czech mainstream media. Romea.cz also runs Roma TV and has a strong social media presence. Its mission is to combat racism, promote human rights and foster understanding between the Roma community and the majority population.

Romea.cz <https://romea.cz/en>

Ireland

The Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy recommends that, in an era of globalisation, people should be able to inform themselves from a local source and recognises the role of community media. Resolutions adopted by citizens call for state support and collaboration between community media and other media organisations, particularly with regard to training.

CRAOL - The National Forum for Community Radio in Ireland

Since its foundation in 1995, CRAOL has served as a network, training facility and lobbying group for Irish community radio. Every week, 2,000 community radio volunteers broadcast to 170,000 people across Ireland through 21 fully licensed stations and almost 30 aspirant stations.

As a signatory to the AMARC Europe Charter, CRAOL's primary aim is to empower community broadcasters to deliver social benefits to their communities through active volunteering, shared resources, good governance, partnerships, and networking.

The community radio stations belonging to CRAOL are non-profit organisations, owned and managed by their communities. They promote inclusion, diversity, participation, and democracy.

CRAOL <https://craol.ie/>

Saturday Chronicles

Saturday Chronicles is a Community Radio show on Scariff Bay Community Radio based in Scariff, Co. Clare, promoting democracy and encouraging media literacy. It won the CRAOL Gold Medal in the Social Benefit and News category in 2025.

Scariff Bay Community Radio Podcasts SBCR

<https://scariffbayradiopodcasts.podbean.com/e/live-from-brussels%C2%A0-%C2%A0-interview-highlights-liam-hayes/>

Slovenia

Recognising the democratic importance of media participation, the Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in Slovenia calls for citizens and civil society to be actively involved in agenda-setting, for a plurality of voices with legally guaranteed participation of women, minorities, and other underrepresented groups, and for the encouragement and support of grassroots and community media as platforms for democratic engagement, alongside education and policies that empower all citizens.

Oštro – Public editorial meetings

Oštro, a non-profit investigative media outlet, regularly organises public editorial meetings. Citizens are invited to participate in discussions about editorial priorities, story selection and journalistic dilemmas. These meetings increase transparency around the decision-making processes involved in journalism and introduce participants to the standards of investigative journalism, fact-checking and ethical responsibility. They also create meaningful opportunities for citizens to engage with journalism beyond passive consumption.

Oštro <https://www.ostro.si>

Radio Študent – Media production by marginalised groups

Radio Študent is a non-profit community radio station that gives citizens and marginalised and minority communities the opportunity to create and broadcast their own radio shows. The station provides access to media production tools and editorial support, as well as an established public platform. This enables groups that are often underrepresented in mainstream media to express their perspectives, cultural identities, and political concerns and to participate in the public debate.

Radio Študent <https://radiostudent.si>

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